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CREATION OF NEW TYPES OF RABBITS IN AZERBAIJAN AND STUDYING THE QUALITY INDICATORS OF THEIR MEAT

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Abstract

Breeding has its own characteristics when creating a new breed using crossbreeding in rabbits. The sexes used in the first stage are selected without signs of kinship. The selection of breeds is based on economic weight, quality of fur, durability, early maturity and propensity for meat.

The second stage is more difficult in creating breed. This is the creation of different and desirable types within the derived generation according to more prominent features.

Based on the above, the following rules were taken into account during the crossing.

1. Matching breeds are selected;
2. More productive animals were used;
3. The target is set correctly;
4. More qualitative features have been strengthened [1; 2].

If we look at the live weight of 2nd generation of litters (F_2) obtained by homogeneous crossbreeding, we can say that the live weight of rabbits at 3 months (bucks and does) is 390; 130 g was higher than the live weight of the 1st generation litters. This risk is also observed in litters obtained without hybridization.

Keywords: breeding, rabbit breeds, new types of rabbits by fur, rabbit meat quality indicators, rabbit meat composition

INTRODUCTION

Rabbit breeding is developing in Azerbaijan as a new little-studied type of livestock industry. The prospects of this industry lies in the fact that rabbits have high fertility, adaptability, precocity, their meat has high nutritional value, and skin and down are valuable raw materials. So, in a year from one rabbit you can get 60-70 kg of meat, 25-30 pieces of skins and about 1 kg of fluff.

The according to the State Statistics Committee of Azerbaijan, as the 1st of January 2020th, there were 28,511 rabbits in the country (of which 2,350 were maternal rabbits). Rabbit breeding is widespread in Ganja-Kazakh, Sheki-Zagatala, Guba-Khachmaz, as well as in lowland regions and Nakhichevan Autonomous Republic. In these regions, the Californian, New Zealand breed, meat breed, leather-fur, white and gray Giant, Silver, Japanese, Marder breed, Dutch, Angora, Decorative Dwarf rabbit breeds are mainly bred [3].

MATERIALS AND METHODS OF SCIENTIFIC WORK

In rabbit breeding, unlike other branches of animal husbandry, in scientific research aimed at obtaining new species, there is a need to use various breeding methods. Here the grouping of rabbit is carried out for crossing on a selective basis.

Two breeding methods are used in rabbit breeding:

1. breeding in purity;
2. crossing.

When breeding clean, male and female rabbits should be of the same breed. For breeding works on highly productive breeds of rabbits, a pure breeding method is of great importance. The biological peculiarity of this method lies in the fact that purebred rabbit breeds consistently inherit their inherent characteristics and qualities from their offspring and further consolidating this hereditary quality. When breeding any purebred breeds in rabbit breeding, the following main goals are set:

1. To preserve and strengthen the high productivity and breeding quality of the breed;
2. increasing the number of breeds;
3. improvement of breeds.

The results of many studies in rabbit breeding show that the use of the method of breeding in purity leads to an increase in their breeding qualities, fixing the hereditary traits acquired by rabbits [4; 5; 6; 7; 8; 9; 10].

When crossing, using rabbit breeds with high indicators of constitution, exterior and productivity, it is possible to obtain new popular crossbreeds.

For this purpose, in the "Rabbit breeding farm" The Scientific Research Institute of Animal Husbandry of the Republic of Azerbaijan carried out research work on the creation of new types of rabbits in the fur-skin-meat direction. Decorative Dwarf, Californian, Japanese and New Zealand rabbit breeds were used in the research.

THE RESULTS OBTAINED AND THE ANALYSIS

The purpose of the research work is to preserve and consolidate the high productive and breeding qualities of the breeds used, increase their numbers, create new types of rabbits, study their growth and development, and meat quality indicators. For this purpose, a crossing was carried out on 12.09.2019 and crossbreeds were obtained. The resulting rabbits are not similar in color to either the maternal or paternal breed. He is active, has black and gray color, furry skin, white tips of the legs, straight posture and is prone to fleshiness. The rest of the crossbreeds are gray-brown. Two livestock

(females) of the offspring acquired on 03.16.2020 are white, and two livestock (males) are gray.

At the following stages, the Japanese breed was taken as a heterotic breed for both homogeneous and heterogeneous crossing. The color of the crossbreeds (F_1 x Japanese breed) obtained from homogeneous crossing is mainly black and gray spotted. Black rabbits have shades of gray on the pads of their paws. The color is monochrome, the fluff is delicate, and the rabbit itself is precocious.

As a result of heterogeneous crossing on 28.09.2020, 9 (F_1 generation crossbreed x Japanese breed) were obtained hybrid. In this offspring there are black, gray-chestnut, black-andwhite, gray rabbits with the same color shades. In accordance with the conditions of the research work, descendants of only black and gray color were selected. The color of black-graybrown rabbits are of the same type. They have shades of gray on their paws, a black spot on the rabbit's forehead, the inner part of the ear, the mirror of the nose, the lower part of the abdomen (completely), the pad of the paws and the circumference of the neck are white. The rest of the body is black and the skin is tender.

On the 1st of June, 2021st, an interlinear hybridization was carried out and the resulting hybrids were evaluated. So, the color of one livestock obtained as a result of interlinear hybridization is brown, there are white stripes on the neck, the tips of the front paws are white, prone to fleshiness, the skin is fur, the rest of the descendants are of the same type, the color is gray (table 1; fig. 1)

Table 1.

Comparative indicators of the status of parents and the resulting hybrid at different ages

Indicators	Age		
	Mother in 3 months	Father in 3 months	Rabbit hybrid in 3 months
Live weight, kg	1,295	1,425	1,540
Straight trunk length, cm	29,0	32,0	38,0
Chest width	6,0	7,0	8,0
Chest girth	21,0	25,0	28,0
Croup width	7,0	9,0	11
Ear length	6,0	6,5	8,5
Ear width	3,5	3,8	5,5

Fig. 1. Comparison of the indicators of the resulting hybrid with the indicators of the does and bucks

As can be seen from the table, the live weight of a hybrid rabbit at the age of 3 months, respectively, is 245 g more than the live weight of the mother and 115 g more than the live weight of the father. Excess live weight contributes to the production of more meat. Therefore, at the next stage of research, the meat productivity of the obtained rabbits and the quality indicators of meat were studied in comparison with maternal and paternal lines.

As we know, unlike other animal products, rabbit meat contains little cholesterol, fat and relatively more protein. In terms of the amount of muscle mass contained in rabbit meat, it is inferior to other farm animals. Rabbit meat refers to a type of white meat. Rabbit meat is rich in proteins, minerals and vitamins [11; 12; 13; 14; 15; 16].

Due to the digestibility, rabbit meat is absorbed by the body up to 90%, while the digestibility of beef is 62%. The ratio of meat and bone in the carcass is 15-17%, whereas in cattle this indicator is 20-25%. Muscle tissue-as the main part of meat, has great nutritional value. Therefore, the more muscle tissue in the carcass, the higher the nutritional value of the meat [17; 18; 19; 20].

While horses have 60-65% of the total weight, cattle 57-62%, sheep 50-60%, pigs 40-52%, broiler

chickens 51-53%, rabbits on average 84-85% of the total weight is muscle tissue. Rabbit meat contains an average of 21,5% protein. As for lamb, this diagram is 16,4%, in pork-16,5%, in veal and chicken meat-20%, and in beef – 20,5%. The meat of young rabbits contains 74-77% moisture, 15-19% protein, 5-6% fat and 1.0-1.1% minerals. In the meat of 3-5-month-old rabbits, the fat and protein content reaches 8%, and the calorie content is 150-190 kcal. The meat of an adult rabbit contains up to 20 p.c. fat, and its energy value is up to 300 kcal [21; 22; 23; 24; 25; 26; 27].

Rabbit meat contains 19 amino acids. It should be noted the content of some essential amino acids in rabbit meat: lysine-10,43%, and methionine and tryptophan-2,37 and 1,55%, respectively [28; 29; 30; 31; 32].

The quality of meat is assessed by its morphological and chemical composition. The morphological composition of the meat is determined after deboning. The ratio of muscle tissue to bone tissue, muscle tissue to adipose tissue and the amount of muscle tissue and edible part as a percentage is also determined. During the experiment, the yield of carcass meat was determined (table 2; fig. 2). The quality of meat was assessed by the amount of fat and protein contained in it (table 3; fig. 3) [33; 34; 35; 36].

Table 2.

Meat yield in carcass, percent. n=3

Indicators	In crossbreeds			With homogeneous crossing			With heterogeneous crossing			With interlinear hybridization		
	Mother	Father	Descendant	Mother	Father	Descendant	Mother	Father	Descendant	Mother	Father	Descendant
Live weight at 3 months r	1180	1350	1430	1250	1510	1640	1210	1340	1480	1295	1410	1540
Amount of meat, %	85,4	85,9	86,2	84,3	85,3	86,7	83,6	84,6	86,1	82,7	84,6	86,7
The assimilable part, %	70,4	70,9	71,2	69,3	70,3	71,7	68,6	69,3	71,1	67,7	69,6	71,7
Live weight at 4 months	1540	1650	1780	1530	1370	1710	1540	1650	1730	-	-	-
Amount of meat, %	84,0	84,6	86,4	83,2	85,6	86,8	84,3	85,3	86,8	-	-	-
The assimilable part, %	69,0	69,6	71,4	68,2	70,6	71,8	69,3	70,3	71,8	-	-	-

Fig. 2. The yield of carcass meat in 3-months-old crossbreeds

As can be seen from table 2, the digestible part of rabbit crossbred meat at 3 months of age is 0,8% more than the digestible part of does meat and 0,3% more than the digestible part of bucks rabbit meat. And at the

age of 4 months, this indicator was 2,4%; 1,8%, respectively. These data are superior in descendants obtained both from homogeneous and heterogeneous crossing and from interline hybridization [37].

Table 3.

Comparative indicators of amino acid content in meat of 3-month-old rabbits with parents, mg/kg, n=3

Amino acids	Crossbreeds			With homogeneous crossing			With heterogeneous crossing			With interlinear hybridization		
	Mother	Father	Descendant	Mother	Father	Descendant	Mother	Father	Descendant	Mother	Father	Descendant
Isoleucine	38,5	41,3	45,8	37,5	40,4	44,8	37,8	45,8	54,3	31,2	48,8	55,4
Methionine + cystine	57,8	68,2	70,4	57,6	58,6	71,3	57,8	68,4	71,3	57,6	58,2	71,4
Phenylalanine+ Tyrosine	38,5	49,2	50,4	38,3	48,4	50,5	38,4	49,3	51,3	38,7	49,8	51,5
Tyrosine	55,2	61,3	63,4	56,6	58,6	63,4	56,0	56,5	58,1	52,5	53,2	55,7
Threonine	39,09	41,97	44,96	32,2	38,1	42,0	38,1	41,7	44,8	38,2	41,5	44,6
Valin	48,0	50,3	55,4	47,8	50,6	52,8	48,8	55,3	58,0	46,8	48,3	52,0
Total:	277,09	312,27	330,36	270,0	294,7	324,8	246,9	317,0	337,8	265	299,8	330,5

Fig. 3. Amino acid content in meat of 3-months-old crossbreeds

When analyzing the chemical composition of rabbit meat, it was revealed that the protein content in the meat of crossbreeds is 2,6% higher than in the meat of mother rabbits, and 2,2% more than in the meat of father rabbits. This indicator is also high for the rest of the descendants.

The results obtained

– It can be seen from the results that in the study of amino acids in 1 kg of crossbreed meat, 53.27 mg more was determined than in the meat of does, and 18,09 mg more than in the meat of bucks. These indicators were also revealed in offspring obtained from both homogeneous and heterogeneous crossing and from interline hybridization.

– From the above, it can be concluded that the live weight and quality indicators of the meat of the created rabbit species exceed the corresponding indicators of the does and bucks. Here the key role is played by the selection and purposeful breeding of rabbits of the same species. It also allows you to get better rabbit meat, containing relatively more full-fledged proteins and essential amino acids.

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